

Significantly Improved Detection of Molecular Oxygen by Two-Color Resonance-Enhanced Multiphoton Ionization

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Abstract

We report a new spectroscopic detection scheme for molecular oxygen that achieves roughly two orders of magnitude higher sensitivity for fully rotationally resolved spectra than the current state of the art. By implementing two-color ($2 + 1'$) resonance-enhanced multiphoton ionization (REMPI) via the $3d$ Rydberg complex, state-selective spectra with signal comparable to the intense but diffuse $C\ 3s\sigma\ ^3\Pi_g \leftarrow X\ ^3\Sigma_g^-$ ($2 + 1$) REMPI bands were obtained without significant saturation or broadening. The resulting increase in sensitivity permitted observation of the very weak $3d\pi\ ^1\Delta_2 \leftarrow X\ ^3\Sigma_g^-$ transitions and is independent of the intermediate state. This advance in ionization efficiency and quantum-state-selective sensitivity for O_2 promises to aid physical and chemical studies across a wide variety of fields.

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Molecular oxygen is vital for human life and pivotal in many chemical processes on Earth and beyond.¹ In several research areas, including ultracold chemistry,²⁻⁴ combustion,^{5,6} plasma,^{7,8} atmospheric chemistry,⁹ surface scattering,^{10,11} new physics searches,^{12,13} and astrochemistry,^{14,15} quantum state-resolved data is necessary to reveal the physical and chemical dynamics of O_2 . The unique and ubiquitous chemistry of oxygen results from its biradical electronic structure, which also creates severe challenges for spectroscopic detection. In this Letter, we describe a new detection scheme that addresses these difficulties, allowing for fully rotationally resolved detection of molecular oxygen with unprecedented sensitivity.

State-of-the-art oxygen detection employs single-color ($2 + 1$) resonance-enhanced multiphoton ionization (REMPI) [Figure 1(a,b)]. Since molecular oxygen possesses no strong

allowed transitions at wavelengths longer than the vacuum ultraviolet, most schemes are based on two photon ultraviolet (UV) studies,¹⁶⁻²⁵ which mapped many O₂ Rydberg states. This approach is often augmented by time-of-flight mass-spectrometry (TOFMS), providing mass selectivity, high sensitivity, and rovibrational resolution. Unfortunately, the excited states suitable for one-color REMPI typically suffer from one or more drawbacks, including predissociation, broad linewidths, or low excitation cross-sections, which pose challenges for detection schemes of O₂ in terms of efficiency and state selectivity.

The acute need for improved spectroscopic methods to ionize and detect O₂ has been raised across a variety of physical and chemical fields. In molecular interaction experiments, decelerating and trapping atoms or molecules enable studies of collisions, state selectivity, high-density molecular quantum gases, and long-range interactions. In one such study, Wiederkehr *et al.*² described the difficulties involved in detecting molecular oxygen and the advantages of transitions to low rotational levels of the anomalous $C\ 3s\sigma\ ^3\Pi_g\ (v' = 2)$ state near 287.6 nm [Figure 1(b)] due to their relatively long lifetimes and smaller predissociative character. Nonetheless, the rotational structure is only partially resolved even when relatively low laser powers are employed to avoid degrading resolution (i.e., minimizing power broadening and AC Stark effects) at the expense of ionization efficiency. In similar contexts, a $C\ 3s\sigma\ ^3\Pi_g$ scheme was also utilized by Karpov *et al.*,³ who along with Akerman *et al.*⁴ noted the need for improved detection schemes for molecular oxygen. In the field of combustion, laser ignition of fuel-air mixtures via REMPI ionization schemes of O₂ has demonstrated inherent advantages over conventional spark and thermal methods.²⁶ Dumitrache *et al.*²⁷ recently showed that the improvement in electron generation by resonant ~ 287.6 nm ionization over non-resonant 266 nm increased efficiency, extended the lean limit, and reduced laser power requirements. Molecular oxygen is also critical in gas-surface chemistry, where state-selective detection of O₂ can grant insight into processes such as oxidation. Nevertheless, it is often unmeasured or characterized by suboptimal means. For example, Nakamura and Kitajima¹⁰ measured only a non-resonant signal of O₂ at 266 nm, while Ambaye *et al.*¹¹

resorted to nitric oxide as a more easily detected substitute. Altogether, these diverse examples make clear the broad and pressing need for enhanced spectroscopic detection methods for O_2 . Here we present the discovery of a two-color REMPI scheme for molecular oxygen that delivers state-selective detection capabilities with significantly improved sensitivity, promising to aid in many physical and chemical studies.

Figure 1: Resonance-enhanced multiphoton ionization (REMPI) schemes used for molecular oxygen detection. (2 + 1) REMPI at (a) 223 – 237 nm and (b) ~ 287.6 nm, and (c) the proposed (2 + 1') REMPI scheme at 223 – 237 nm with an added visible or infrared ionizing photon at or below 1304 – 771 nm, depending on the excited intermediate state.

Our two-color (2 + 1') REMPI scheme excites a $3d$ Rydberg state using UV radiation, followed by visible (VIS) or infrared (IR) absorption to ionize O_2 molecules slightly above threshold [Figure 1(c)]. The dramatic two orders of magnitude improvement in sensitivity is apparent when comparing (2 + 1') and (2 + 1) REMPI scans covering the $3d$ Rydberg state spectral region, independent of the intermediate state; the $3d\pi^3\Sigma_0^-$ ($v' = 0$) region previously assigned by Haiyoon *et al.*¹⁹ is displayed in Figure 2(a) [Full coverage is shown in Figure S1 in the Supporting Information]. The addition of the intense (15 – 25 mJ) VIS beam had little effect on noise and non-resonant signal, considerably improving the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The increase in signal and SNR is even more striking when low or high UV fluences fail to saturate the two-photon transition or result in noise and non-resonant ionization, respectively. The relative intensities follow those obtained by one-color REMPI under similar conditions, and the enhancement appears independent of the 1' wavelength over a broad range. We expect the $4s$ and $5s-4d$ Rydberg complexes accessible at higher UV photon energies will exhibit similar or improved behavior.

Figure 2: Spectra recorded via resonance-enhanced multiphoton ionization (REMPI) schemes of O_2 : (a) single-color ultraviolet (UV) $(2 + 1)$ REMPI of the $3d\pi\ ^3\Sigma_0^-$ at ~ 0.7 mJ (red), and two-color $(2 + 1')$ REMPI with ~ 0.7 mJ UV power and ~ 20 mJ visible power at 760 nm (blue), where the baseline of the latter is shifted upwards for clarity; (b) $(2 + 1')$ REMPI at higher (~ 1.4 mJ) UV laser power (dark cyan) compared to the blue trace from (a); and (c) $(2 + 1)$ REMPI of the $C\ 3s\sigma\ ^3\Pi_g\ (v' = 2)$ F_3 state at ~ 3.5 (green) and ~ 25 (dark yellow) mJ UV power.

To further demonstrate the efficacy of the approach, two-color $(2 + 1')$ REMPI scans (blue trace in Figure 3) show well-defined features corresponding to the very weak $3d\pi\ ^1\Delta_2 \leftarrow X\ ^3\Sigma_g^-\ (v' = 0, 1)$ transitions. The $3d\pi\ ^1\Delta_2$ states were previously assigned;²¹ however, their detection and assignment had to be performed from the metastable $a^1\Delta_g$ state since $(2 + 1)$ REMPI from the ground electronic state lacked the sensitivity to confidently assign them, even with a 50 – 150 shot average.^{17–19} In comparison, the $3d\pi\ ^1\Delta_2$ state is clearly visible in a single $(2 + 1')$ REMPI scan with only a 4 shot average.

The considerably improved performance of the $(2 + 1')$ REMPI scheme likely arises from multiple factors. Increased ionization step flux via non-resonant low-energy photons significantly improves upon the limited laser power available in the deep UV,^{28–30} while reducing non-resonant signal, broadening, predissociation, and dissociation. Ionization to lower cation internal energies could benefit from broad autoionization slightly above (~ 0.8 eV) the cation ground state,^{31,32} and less dissociative ionization, although generally we see little of the latter when simultaneously monitoring the mass-gated atomic oxygen signal. Two-color REMPI signals attributed to dissociative ionization were observed only for two

Figure 3: Partial resonance-enhanced multiphoton ionization (REMPI) spectra of the $3d\pi$ Rydberg state for $(v' = 0, 1)$. The blue traces display two-color $(2 + 1')$ REMPI signals of molecular oxygen (~ 5 K), ionized at ~ 760 nm. The traces are single scans (4 shot average) without post-processing. The insets show the $3d\pi \ ^1\Delta_2 \leftarrow X \ ^3\Sigma_g^-$ ($v' = 0, 1$) Rydberg transitions, respectively, enlarged and smoothed. The green traces are a digitized version of the $(2 + 1)$ REMPI results by Haiyoon *et al.*¹⁹ with 50 to 150 laser shots averaged.

transitions (near $43,627$ and $43,631$ cm^{-1}) via the $3d\pi \ ^3\Sigma_1^+$ ($v' = 1$) states¹⁷ (Figure S1 in the Supporting Information); these coincidences could presumably be avoided by varying the VIS photon energy. At ~ 225 nm, where both atomic and molecular oxygen are resonantly ionized,^{33,34} we observed a decrease in the O^+ signal with the introduction of the VIS beam, likely indicative of the entire spectral range.

Ordinarily, an additional laser beam adds undesirable experimental complexity. However, since tabletop tunable lasers predominantly generate UV radiation via frequency conversion, the practical complications of a two-color process can be mitigated by utilizing the laser fundamental as the second color source. This simplification is possible since the only constraint on the VIS or IR radiation is reaching the ionization threshold. We have tested this approach, and merely note that one must be careful to maintain temporal and spatial overlap, especially with dispersive optical elements.

In cases where signal is the sole concern, transitions to the $C \ 3s\sigma \ ^3\Pi_g$ states are typically used; they lie near 287.6 nm [Figure 2(c)] and are more intense than the $3d$ Rydberg transitions. Nevertheless, their broad and congested nature [resulting from predissociation³⁵

and often exacerbated by the high laser powers employed to saturate the transitions and maximize raw signal; [Figure 2\(c\)](#)] makes it difficult to retrieve any spectroscopic information, and broadening effects often limit their peak resonant signal. Under our conditions, the signal for the $C\ 3s\sigma\ ^3\Pi_g$ states plateaued for pulse energies above ~ 20 mJ ([Figure S2](#) in the Supporting Information). It is worth noting that in principle, $(2 + 1')$ REMPI can be applied to the $C\ 3s\sigma\ ^3\Pi_g$ states as well. The scheme then requires ionizing photons below 359 nm, for which 355 nm from a frequency-tripled Nd:YAG is a prime candidate. Higher signals should be possible using a two-color scheme; however, a high flux of 355 nm radiation could also be expected to produce non-resonant signal and broadening. Furthermore, since available 287.6 nm laser sources can already saturate the transition, and the fundamental issue of congestion will remain, the improvement is likely to be far less drastic. In contrast, $(2 + 1')$ REMPI of the $3d$ Rydberg complex enables the acquisition of rotationally resolved spectral information from many narrow features over a broad spectral range with high SNR. Additionally, at our highest available deep UV power (~ 1.4 mJ), $(2 + 1')$ REMPI [dark cyan trace in [Figure 2\(b\)](#)] already exhibits comparable signals to $(2 + 1)$ REMPI via the $C\ 3s\sigma\ ^3\Pi_g$ state while remaining far from significant broadening or saturation. Thus, a more powerful laser source will allow even higher $(2 + 1')$ signals to be obtained. For comparison, under nominal conditions (~ 1.1 and ~ 25 mJ of UV and VIS power, respectively) for both signal strength and SNR the most intense $3d\pi\ ^3\Sigma_0^-$ $(2 + 1')$ REMPI transition ($42,636\text{ cm}^{-1}$) has $\sim 10\times$ better SNR, two orders of magnitude better resonant to non-resonant signal ratio, and similar signal strength to the $C\ 3s\sigma\ ^3\Pi_g$ $(2 + 1)$ REMPI scheme.

We presented a new two-color $(2 + 1')$ REMPI scheme with significantly increased sensitivity and the capability to collect quantum state resolved information over a broad spectral range. We anticipate that the method's high SNR and sensitivity in state-selective experiments will enable the extraction of new information about molecular oxygen dynamics in a variety of physical and chemical research directions.

METHODS

Supersonic expansion of pure oxygen gas (1 bar backing pressure) delivered by a pulsed valve (General Valve Series 9) with a 0.79 mm conic orifice and driven by an Iota One[®] controller with 400 μ s opening time generates the molecular beam (MB). The MB passes through two skimmers 1.09 and 1.0 mm in diameter at 7 and 20 cm downstream, respectively. The resulting MB has a low internal temperature of ~ 5 K. We perform the two-color ($2 + 1'$) and one-color ($2 + 1$) REMPI using a tunable frequency-tripled pulsed dye laser (Lioptec, LiopStar-E-N with LSEH extension, 0.04 cm^{-1} linewidth, 0.65 – 1.4 mJ) pumped by a frequency-doubled Nd:YAG laser (InnoLas, Spotlight 1200, 250 mJ) for the UV beam and a tunable fundamental pulsed dye laser (Sirah, Cobra-Stretch, 0.04 cm^{-1} linewidth, 15 – 25 mJ) pumped by another similar frequency-doubled Nd:YAG laser for the VIS beam. The lasers produce 7 ns pulses at a 20 Hz repetition rate and are horizontally polarized. The respective counterpropagating UV and VIS beams are focused by 20 and 25.4 cm focal length plano-convex lenses and intersect the MB at 90° . The two beams overlap spatially and temporally, and the densest and coldest MB section is selected by controlling the delays between the pulsed valve and the pump laser Q-switches via a delay generator (Stanford Research, DG645). The REMPI signal detection is accomplished by a reflectron TOFMS (Jordan TOF Products, C-0726) passed through a $200\times$ pre-amplifier (ORTEC, VT120A) and recorded by monitoring mass-gated signals on an oscilloscope.

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Supporting Information Available

Two-color ($2 + 1'$) REMPI spectra of the $3d$ Rydberg complex of O_2 (Figure S1) and one-color ($2 + 1$) REMPI spectra of the $C\ 3s\sigma\ ^3\Pi_g \leftarrow X\ ^3\Sigma_g^-$ ($v' = 2$) transition of O_2 (Figure S2).

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